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International sea turtle funded projects

[Project \(PRJ\)](#) | **Pacific Islands Regional Office (PIRO)**

GUID: gov.noaa.nmfs.inport:21996 | Updated: August 9, 2022 | Published / External

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Item Identification

Title: International sea turtle funded projects

Short Name: International sea turtle projects

Status: In Work

Abstract: PIRO may fund activities for the conservation, protection, and recovery of ESA-listed sea turtle species in international locations. As noted within the U.S. Sea Turtle Recovery Plans, some recovery tasks do not necessarily apply to areas within jurisdiction of the U.S., but must be addressed to recover the species. Tasks in international locations are intended to benefit aggregations of sea turtles that have documented linkages to the PIR, are impacted by PIR activities managed by NOAA/NMFS, or projects that are relevant and applicable to NOAA/NMFS management and ESA recovery obligations. Since 2008, internationally funded projects have occurred (taken place) in Malaysia, Cook Islands, Solomon Islands, Vanuatu, Papua New Guinea, Japan, and Mexico.

Purpose: To contribute to the conservation and recovery of sea turtle species with documented linkages to the PIR, which include: leatherback (*Dermochelys coriacea*), hawksbill (*Eretmochelys imbricata*), North and South Pacific loggerhead (*Caretta caretta*) Distinct Population Segments, olive ridley (*Lepidochelys olivacea*), and green turtle (*Chelonia mydas*).

Notes: Implementation schedule: 2008 - present

Projects range from nesting beach monitoring, educational outreach, and fishery mitigation to reduce sea turtle bycatch.

Supplemental Information: Funding organization: PIRO.

Support Roles

Point of Contact

CC ID: 172816

Date Effective From: 2008

Date Effective To:

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Catalog Details

Catalog Item ID: 21996

GUID: gov.noaa.nmfs.inport:21996

Metadata Record Created By: Irene K Kelly

Metadata Record Created: 2014-07-24 19:16+0000

Metadata Record Last Modified By: SysAdmin InPortAdmin

Metadata Record Last Modified:	2022-08-09 17:11+0000
Metadata Record Published:	2015-12-01
Owner Org:	PIRO
Metadata Publication Status:	Published Externally
Do Not Publish?:	N
Metadata Last Review Date:	2015-12-01
Metadata Review Frequency:	1 Year
Metadata Next Review Date:	2016-12-01

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Build FINAL (2025-12-02 18:25 UTC)

